

Embargo Notice for Scientific Article

Title of the Article: Oral quercetin supplementation hampers skeletal muscle adaptations in response to exercise training

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To Whom It May Concern,

This document serves as a formal notice that the scientific article titled “Oral quercetin supplementation hampers skeletal muscle adaptations in response to exercise training”, is currently under embargo.

The embargo is in place as per the terms and conditions of Journal of Scandinavian Journal of Medicine and Science in Sports and will last until further notice. During the embargo period, the article cannot be publicly shared or disseminated through any digital or print medium.

Thank you for your understanding and cooperation.

Sincerely,

Rafael A. Casuso